

Pauli Matrices Versus A Vector Dot Product/ Square Root Combination

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After the discovery of $\partial/\partial t$ partial and $-i\partial/\partial x$ partial as energy and momentum operators in quantum mechanics, Dirac linearized the Klein-Gordon equation to obtain 4x4 matrices based on Pauli 2x2 matrices. As a result, a quantum spin degree of freedom emerged from theory, and matched experimental results.

Given the Lorentz invariant form: $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ ($c=1$), one may mathematically write: $E = \pm \sqrt{p^2 + m^2}$, which is standard procedure. One may ask: What is wrong with this expression? We argue in this note that it is not incorrect, but rather incomplete mathematics for the reason that one has to insert \pm by hand. We suggest that a complete mathematical description of the square root of a dot product $p \cdot p$ should automatically give rise to two solutions associated with \pm . Thus, Dirac's linearization is not simply a procedure for finding spin, but, we suggest, is a more complete mathematical approach to describing the square root of $p \cdot p$, which holds even if one does not consider physical situations. Interestingly, nature seems to choose this more complete mathematical description rather than the looser one using the $\sqrt{\quad}$ function and the manually inserted \pm signs.

Traditional Square Root

It is well known that the square root of a positive number bb has two values $+b$ and $-b$ which corresponds to a mapping of two points (one on the positive x axis and the other on the negative) into the same positive number bb . The issue, we argue, is that one has to "remember" there are two solutions and manually insert \pm .

$P \cdot p$ maps a 3-vector into a positive number. One may always align the z axis with the p vector (through a rotation of the co-ordinate axes) and so $p \cdot p = |p||p| = \text{positive number}$. One may consider taking the square root of such a number to obtain two solutions, i.e. by manually inserting \pm

$$\pm \sqrt{p \cdot p} \quad ((1))$$

$P \cdot p$ may be obtained using 3-vectors as basis vectors i.e. $e_x = (1,0,0)$, $e_y = (0,1,0)$ and $e_z = (0,0,1)$. This is the traditional mathematical approach employed, i.e. ((1)) and 3-vector basis vectors. Our main objection to this procedure is that the mathematics does not produce the \pm solutions automatically, but that these have to be inserted by hand. We suggest that a more complete mathematical approach would naturally yield the two solutions \pm . We suggest this is what the approach of Dirac does. Thus, the linearization of $p \cdot p$ using matrices is a more complete way of describing a square root mathematically which naturally demonstrates the existence of the two solutions \pm . In other words, this linearization may be applied to math situations even if there is no physics (spin) present.

More Complete Square Root

We suggest there should exist a more complete math formalism to describing the square root of $p \cdot p$ which supplants the use of the square root symbol, dot product and the manually inserted +/- . In particular, the two solution possibilities + and - should appear automatically from the math. One knows that matrices may have eigenvalue/eigenfunction solutions. A 2x2 matrix (with appropriate properties) may have two distinct eigenvalues (+1,-1) and two eigenfunctions corresponding to the two solutions required in a square root.

For simplicity, consider only $p \cdot p = pz \cdot pz = (-pz)(-pz)$. If one writes the generalized number, i.e. matrix expression:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{bmatrix} pz = sz \cdot pz \quad \text{then} \quad \begin{bmatrix} pz & pz \\ sz & sz \end{bmatrix} = pz \cdot pz \cdot I \quad \text{where } I \text{ is the identity matrix ((2))}$$

$Sz \cdot pz$ represents the square root if one also includes its eigenfunction. For (1,0) one has:

$$Pz \cdot sz (1,0) = pz (+1) (1,0) \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{but for } (0,1) \text{ one has: } \begin{bmatrix} pz & sz \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = (-1) \begin{bmatrix} pz & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad ((3b))$$

The two required square root solutions (associated with +/-) naturally appear. This approach, however, only holds for pz i.e. the p vector aligned with the z axis. What happens if one has the full (px, py, pz) ? Can one retain the +/- natural feature of sz as well as the orthogonality of px, py, pz which traditionally arises from multiplying the basis vectors (1,0,0), (0,1,0) and (0,0,1)?

To see if this is possible one may write:

$$Sx \cdot px + sy \cdot py + sz \cdot pz = A \quad \text{such that} \quad A(\text{transpose}) A = p \cdot p \quad ((4)) \quad \text{Then:}$$

$$Sx(*,t) \cdot sx = sy(*,t) \cdot sy = sz(*,t) \cdot sz = 1 \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$sx(*,t) \cdot sy + sy(*,t) \cdot sx = sx(*,t) \cdot sz + sz(*,t) \cdot sx + sy(*,t) \cdot sz + sz(*,t) \cdot sy = 0 \quad ((5b))$$

=complex conjugate and t the transpose. Note: $sz(,t) = sz$.

It is well known that the Pauli matrices satisfy ((5)) with sz being given in ((2)).

If one wishes $sz \cdot s + s(\text{transpose}) \cdot sz = 0$ then for:

$$s = \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow \begin{bmatrix} 2a & b-c \\ c & -c+b-2d \end{bmatrix} = 0 \quad ((6a)) \quad \text{or } a=d=0 \text{ and } b=c \quad \text{i.e. a second real matrix is } \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad ((6b))$$

One, however, requires 3 matrices and there exist only two orthonormal real ones.

Given that one wishes to have $p \cdot p$ as a real number, with ((5a)), one could in principle have: $s^*(\text{transpose}) \cdot s = 1$ with $*$ representing a complex conjugate. A pure imaginary number as opposed to real numbers implies a different dimension and is not necessarily a problem.

For $s_1 = \begin{vmatrix} |e & f| \\ |g & h| \end{vmatrix}$ using $s_z s_1 + s_1 (* \text{ transpose}) s_z = 0$ yields: $\begin{vmatrix} |e+e^* & f-g^*| \\ |-g+f^* & -h+h^*| \end{vmatrix} = 0$

with $e=h=0$, $f=-i$ and $g=i$ as a solution. Then s_1 anticommutes with s_z and s .

In both the case of s_z , s_1 and s ,

$s_z (* \text{ transpose}) s_z = s (* \text{ transpose}) s = s_1 (* \text{ transpose}) s_1 = I$ the identity matrix.

As a result, one may find three 2x2 matrices which have a modulus of 1 and are orthonormal. In other words, these 2x2 matrices yield a complete mathematical description of the square root of $p \cdot p$. They describe the orthogonality of the x-y-z axes, but at the same time mathematically introduce the +/- square root piece which is traditionally added by hand.

We suggest that using Pauli matrices to describe the square root of $p \cdot p$ contains more information and is a more complete approach than the traditional approach of ((1)), although the Pauli matrix approach does not actually yield a single number (or the +/- numbers), but rather a more detailed picture of a system. In the case of a spin .5 fermion, this approach describes physical spin which does not appear in the approach of ((1)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the traditional approach of ((1)) i.e. +/- sqrt($p \cdot p$) is not mathematically complete because one manually adds +/- instead of having these two values naturally appear. This holds both for a number and for $p \cdot p$ which relies on the 3-vectors (1,0,0), (0,1,0), (0,0,1). We seek a mathematical solution which automatically renders +/- . As a simplification, we first consider the number p_z squared which has solutions $-p_z$ and p_z . We suggest that a 2x2 matrix $s = \begin{vmatrix} |1 & 0| \\ |0 & -1| \end{vmatrix}$ naturally yields the +/- solutions through its eigenvalues.

Then, $p_z s$ operating on either (1,0) or (0,1) is a square root solution, with $p_z s (\text{transpose}) p_z s = p_z p_z I$ where I is the identity matrix. We further show that one may extend this approach to include three matrices s_x, s_y and s_z which allow one to write $A = p_x s_x + p_y s_y + p_z s_z$ such that $A (* \text{ transpose}) A = p \cdot p I$. Two matrices are real and the third, purely imaginary. This approach seems to be more mathematically complete and should apply to mathematical situations which are not linked to physics. It, however, also applies to a physical situation, namely the spin of a spin .5 fermion such as a nucleon or electron. Thus nature seems to be associated with a more complete (accurate) mathematical description of a square root, rather than the looser one ((1)) which inserts +/- by hand.